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“AN EMPIRICAL STUDY THE STATUS OF POVERTY IN INDIA”

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ABSTRACT

This paper has been attempted to make an analysis the poverty problem in India for growth and development to sustain and compete in Indian economy. Poverty is defined in terms of income, expenses, and nutritional value (calorie intake). The social dimension of poverty is a neglected area of the study. Poverty is rather the social marginalization of a person, household, or group in the community of society rather than insufficient income to meet basic needs. Indeed, insufficient income is one of the marginalizing factors, but not the only one or groups, but marginalized mainstreaming in the country's development process cannot claim economic growth if population groups are marginalized from the periphery of society. The rapid process of economic growth should accelerate access to services such as education and health for all, especially marginalized citizens. The government must also be aware of the importance of small and dead families to the rural population. Poverty leads to many other problems. The relationship between ignorance and poverty and disease and poverty is well established. There are diseases of poverty such as malaria, tuberculosis, diarrhea, and malnutrition. After the poor become ill from poverty, they do not have the means to get quality health care, which requires borrowing money for treatment. Hospital indebtedness that leads to poverty is well documented. complex phenomenon of many dimensions, not just economic. The results of the analysis indicate that there had been a steady may be decrease in poverty in India during the period considered for research. Finally, the concluding remarks regarding reduce poverty and provide appropriate solution in India. This study will be useful for further research the prospects of poverty elimination in India.

Keywords: Indian Economy. Policy-Reform, GDP, Growth & Development

INTRODUCTION

Strides Made for Poverty Elimination in India: Historical Perspectives

It is evident from the table that during the periods between number (i) 1973-74 and 1983-84, (ii) 1983-84 and 1993-94 and also between 1993-94 and 1999 -2000 all the states have experienced negative percentage point changes in the incidence of poverty in varying degrees. The face-wise analysis of percentage point changes in the extent of poverty across the states reveals that over the period between 1973-74 and 1983-84 all the states excepting Bihar have experienced a faster fall in the magnitude of poverty in varying degrees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on the analysis of poverty in India is indeed very rich. Here entire literature has been classified into three broad categories. The first group is concerned with the estimation of the number of people living below the poverty line. In this group to approaches are used viz. (i) income-based or consumption expenditure based method of estimation of headcount ratio (Dandekar and Rath, 1971; Jha, 2000; Radhakrishna and Ray, 2005; Sen, 1996, 2001; Suryanarayana, 2000; Sundram, 2000; Sundram and Tendulkar, 2005; Subramanian, 2005; etc and (ii) calorie based estimation of headcount measure of the consumption and deprivation (Jones and Sen, 2001; Meenakshi and Viswanathan, 2003. Author's own computation from RBI data Pioneered by P.C. M. Nahalanobis. in the 1940s and 1950s.

In a recent paper Marjit et al. (2015a) develop a simple inter-temporal model, based on the above utility function to show that if the poor expect that the distribution of income will be extremely uneven in the future and they will be marginalized in the society.(Marjit et al., 2015)

These are manifested in the ways in which dominant social groups invisibles, seek to impose dominant values, or routinely devalue and disparage certain categories of people.' Such practices have profound effects on those who are treated this way:(Kabeer, 2000)

It is now well recognized by many scholars that a reasonable framework of choice has to deal with the influence of the society on the consumption behavior of the individual. The idea of conspicuous consumption and the so-called Veblen effect have been well known in economics for many years (Veblen 1902). Sivanathan and Petit (2010) have confirmed the fact that individuals are quite sensitive to their relative status in the society and would like to 'mend' their 'self', under constant attack through various social pressures. (ICITKM & 2017, n.d.)

STATEMENTS OF THE PROBLEM

- After reviewing several kinds of literature, it has been concluded that there is some ambiguity in the measurement and determination of poverty and poverty line in India and the global arena. Some of them are mentioned below:
 - Non-classical path of growth in India: There is the cost for jobless growth in India.
 - Manufacturing Dualism in India: The cause distinction between laborers in organized and unorganized sectors in terms of wages rates, social security, work hours .. etc.
- The concept of poverty-Qualitative Vs. Quantitative: The measurement of the

minimum requirement of life in terms of its monetary values across India and the world is server.

- Crony capitalism: The accumulation of wealth in few hands is also a cause of raising the level of poverty.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Based on the literature survey and gaps of the study, the following objectives have been determined as below:

- To analyze the trends and patterns of poverty in India since Independence.
- To suggest further policy measures to overcome the evil of poverty.
- To resolve the paradoxical relation between growth, poverty, and inequality.
- To find out the proximate explanatory factors responsible for the cross-state and cross-time variations in the incidence of poverty.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

we have examined the cross-state and cross-time behavior of growth, poverty, and inequality in India and tried to find out the approximate factors for the cross-state and cross-time variations in the incidence of income poverty for the period from 1973-74 to 2016-17 by using panel data technique. Our study is exclusively based on the secondary data available from the various rounds of NSSO: reports of Planning Commission/NITI Aayog; Economic and political weekly (EPW) Research Foundation database, Reserve Bank of India on-line database; National Accounts Statistics; Census reports.

ANALYSIS OF DATA:

Table 1: Annual Growth Rate of GDP and its Components in India

Year	Agriculture & Allied Activity	Industry	Services	GDP
1951-61	3.029	6.138	4.478	3.901
1961-71	2.313	5.396	4.879	3.726
1971-81	1.495	4.344	4.165	3.088
1981-91	3.395	6.716	6.327	5.375
1991-2001	2.766	5.023	6.463	5.127
2001-2011	3.537	6.299	8.617	7.003
2016- 2017	4.278	8.152	7.454	7.549

Source: Author's own computation from RBI data in absolute figure (in Billions).

Above data shows the non-Classical path of growth story in India since Independence. This is the main cause of jobless growth in India and Poverty.

Table 2: Head Count Estimates of Poverty & Trends in Poverty in India (in Crore)

Years	Rural	Urban	India
1973-74	26.1	6.0	32.1
1977-78	26.4	6.5	32.9
1983-84	25.2	7.1	32.3
1987-88	23.2	7.5	30.0
1993-94	24.4	7.6	32.0
1999-2000	19.3	6.7	26.0
2007-08	17.0	3.0	20.0
2010-11	20.4.	4.6	25.0
2016-17	22.5	5.0	27.5

Source; Economic Survey, Twelfth Five Year Plan

The data shows a trend analysis of poverty in India. In percentage, term poverty has been reduced, but it has been increased in absolute terms due to an increase in population and equality inequalities. The debate on poverty in India has remained mostly in the domain of economists.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION:

The Dynamics behavior of the extent of power clearly reveals that the rate of decline was almost negligible up to 1970 because of failure of the trickle-down hypothesis so that about 51% of our total population lived below the official poverty line in the mid s70s.later since the mid-70s the extent of poverty started declining at a faster space both at the national level and cross-state level such that between 1977-78 and 1987-88 national-level poverty declined to 39% and thereafter by 2009-10 it has reached the figure of 29.8%. Now since the planning commission has changed the methodology of estimation of poverty for 2004-5 and 2009-10 by switching over from Lakdawala methodology to the Tendulkar mythology which covers a broader perspective for measuring poverty we have also used the same estimates for the period 2011-12 and 2016-17 respectively.

The purpose of this paper has been to resolve the paradoxical relation between growth, poverty, and inequality and to find out the proximate explanatory factors responsible for the cross-state and cross-time variations in the incidence of poverty, we undertake panel

regression by using five-yearly Panel data following the linear model and to propose a simple model of choice based on experimental evidence on human behavior as available in experimental social psychology and relate it to the debate on poverty, nutrition and inequality. It is worth mentioning that while analyzing the temporal behavior of incidence of income poverty across the states we have used the planning commission estimates of poverty. The idea has also been to propose a model which could be easily related to classroom discussion demonstrating the fact that models that we often use to analyze.

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